

1 **Post-thaw dilution of *Rhamdia quelen* sperm improves the reproductive success**

2
3 Thales de Souza França^a, Itamar Cossina Gomes^a, Eduardo Antônio Sanches^b, Maritza Pérez
4 Atehortúa^c, Nathalia Santos Teixeira^a, Rômulo Batista Rodrigues^a, Thaiza Rodrigues de Freitas^a,
5 Andrea Giannotti Galuppo^a, Monike Quirino^d, Jhony Lisbôa Benato^a, Thales Lysakowski Flores
6 Machado^a, Lis Santos Marques^a, Ivan Cunha Bustamante-Filho^e, Fernando Pandolfo
7 Bortolozzo^d, Danilo Pedro Streit Jr^{a*}

8 ^a Aquam Research Group, Animal Science Research Program, Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre,
9 RS, 91540-000, Brazil.

10 ^b Fishery Engineering Course and Aquaculture Centre (CAUNESP) São Paulo State University, Registro, São Paulo
11 11900-000, Brazil.

12 ^c Department of Agricultural and Aquacultural Sciences, Faculty of Natural Resources, Catholic University of
13 Temuco, Temuco, 4781312, Chile

14 ^d Dept. Veterinary Medicine, Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, UFRGS, Porto Alegre, Rio Grande do Sul,
15 91540-000, Brazil.

16 ^e Biotechnology Laboratory, University of Vale of Taquari - Univates, Avelio Tallini Street, 171, Lajeado, RS,
17 Brazil

18 **E-mail addresses:** thalesfranca@gmail.com (T. S. F.); itamar_cossina@yahoo.com.br (I. C. G.);
19 eduardo.sanches@unesp.br (E. A. S.); waira122@gmail.com (M. P. A.); nati_st@hotmail.com (N. S. T.);
20 rrodrigues1903@gmail.com (R. B. R.); thaiza.rfreitas@gmail.com (T. R. F.); andreagalpo@yahoo.com.br
21 (A. G. G.); monikequirino@gmail.com (M. Q.); jhonybenato@hotmail.com (J. L. B.);
22 thalesflores@hotmail.com (T. L. F. M.); lismarx@gmail.com (L. S. M.); ivanbustamante@univates.br (I.
23 C. B.); fpbortol@ufrgs.br (F. P. B.) danilo.streit@ufrgs.br (D. P. S. J.).

24 25 ***Corresponding author:**

26 Department Animal Science, Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, UFRGS, Porto Alegre, Rio
27 Grande do Sul, 91540-000, Brazil. Phone: +55 (51) 98403-0011.

28 *E-mail address:* danilo.streit@ufrgs.br (D.P.S.J).

29 This is the accepted manuscript of the article:

30 França, T. S., Gomes, I. C., Sanches, E. A., Pérez-Atehortúa, M., Teixeira, N. S., Rodrigues, R.
31 B., Freitas, T. R., Galuppo, A. G., Quirino, M., Benato, J. L., Machado, T. L. F., Marques, L. S.,
32 Bustamante-Filho, I. C., Bortolozzo, F. P., & Streit Jr., D. P. (2022). Post-thaw dilution of *Rhamdia*
33 *quelen* sperm improves the reproductive success. *Animal Reproduction Science*, 243, 107018.
34 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anireprosci.2022.107018>

37 **Highlights**

- 38 • Post-thaw dilution improved the velocity of sperm.
- 39 • Post-thaw dilution did not affect the membrane integrity/mitochondrial activity.
- 40 • Post-thaw sperm dilution increased fertilization and hatching rates.

41

42

43 **ABSTRACT**

44 The aim was to evaluate the effect of a post-thaw dilution of *Rhamdia quelen* sperm in 1.1%
45 NaCl (325 mOsm kg⁻¹; pH 7.6; 24°C) solution on the quality and reproductive capacity. Sperm
46 from eight males were cryopreservation in nitrogen vapor at -170°C for 18h in 0.25 mL straws in
47 a freezing medium containing 5% fructose, 5% Powdered milk, and 10% methanol. The samples
48 were thawed and post-thaw diluted (1:20) in NaCl solution or not (control). The higher
49 spermatozoa velocities were observed in the post-thaw diluted samples (curvilinear (VCL) - 69±11
50 µm s⁻¹; average path (VAP) - 45±8 µm s⁻¹; straight-line (VSL) - 43±8 µm s⁻¹) compared to the
51 control (VCL - 47±10 µm s⁻¹; VAP - 31±6 µm s⁻¹; VSL - 30±6 µm s⁻¹). Greater straightness (STR),
52 progression (PROG), and beat cross frequency (BCF) were observed in the post-thaw diluted
53 samples (STR - 96±7%; PROG - 666±128 µm; BCF - 42±2 Hz) than in control (STR - 95±5%;
54 PROG - 463±92 µm; BCF - 40±2 Hz). The strongly curled tail was the only morphology change
55 that differ between the post-thaw diluted (5±2%) and control (2±1%). Membrane integrity,
56 mitochondrial activity, and normal larvae rate were not different between treatments. Fertilization
57 and hatching were higher in the post-thaw diluted sperm (93±3%; 82±9%) when compared to
58 control samples (65±13%; 55±17%). **Were used oocytes from one female, limiting these results.**
59 The post-thaw dilution improved the sperm kinetics and reproductive parameters. Thus, this
60 methodology can be included in the sperm cryopreservation protocol for *R. quelen*.

61

62 **Keywords:** Sperm quality; Sperm cryopreservation; South American silver catfish; Artificial
63 fertilization; Hatching, Sperm dilution.

64

65 1. Introduction

66 Fish sperm cryopreservation protocols have been developed in which several substances
67 have been tested to preserve sperm viability during freezing and thawing (Martínez-Páramo et al.,
68 2017). However, but the period after thawing when sperm are in contact with cryoprotective
69 solutions has previously been neglected by researchers. During the freezing/thawing, cells suffer
70 high stress and damage, so permeable cryoprotectants penetrate cells and inhibit this damage, thus
71 these substances are the key to maintaining sperm viability after the cryopreservation process.

72 Permeable cryoprotectants are components present in cryoprotective solutions that prevent
73 ice crystals' formation and reduce cryoinjuries. However, during the thawing process, the rising
74 temperature increases the toxicity of the permeable cryoprotectants to cells (Best, 2015). In
75 mammals, the common method of cryoprotectant removal involves stepwise dilution with a
76 cryoprotectant-free medium, centrifugation, and resuspension of the sperm. These procedures can
77 cause osmotic and physical damage associated with decreased fertilization rates (Alvarez et al.,
78 1993; Alvarenga et al., 2012). Thus, to reduce the damage caused by cryoprotectants while
79 avoiding centrifugation injury, we propose a new technique called post-thaw dilution, where the
80 thawed sperm is diluted immediately after thawing and before fertilization.

81 NaCl has low commercial value, is accessible, and has previously been used as an extender
82 in cryoprotective sperm solutions (Orfão et al., 2011; López et al., 2015) and activating medium
83 (Viveiros and Godinho, 2009) for neotropical fishes. Seminal plasma is an essential factor in
84 maintaining immobility and sperm quality in the reproductive tract (Figueroa et al., 2015).
85 Neotropical fishes have seminal plasma with osmolalities between 216 and 313 mOsm kg⁻¹ (Di
86 Chiacchio et al., 2017), pH between 6.5 and 8.5 (Tabares et al., 2005), and are rich in Na⁺ ions
87 (França et al., 2020; Egger et al., 2021). Therefore, NaCl solution at a concentration of 325 mOsm
88 kg⁻¹ and a pH of 7.6 guarantees the immobility of sperm by promoting conditions similar to seminal
89 plasma. In addition, the presence of NaCl at the time of activation potentiates the sperm kinetic
90 parameters (Viveiros et al., 2019), increasing the chances of fertilization.

91 The South American silver catfish (*Rhamdia quelen*) is one of the native American species
92 with great potential for aquaculture (Valladão et al., 2018) and a commercial species that
93 consumers appreciate (Gil Barcellos et al., 2004). Its culture is performed mainly in Uruguay,
94 Argentina, and Brazil, where 36,017 fish farmers produce this catfish (Peixe-BR, 2020). This
95 species has protocols for artificial reproduction in captivity (Sanches et al., 2011a), and its sperm
96 cryopreservation protocol was defined by Adames et al. (2015), where the post-thaw sperm
97 presented 48.57% of motility, 58.56% of fertilization rate, and 48.02% of hatching rate. Therefore,
98 this study aimed to evaluate the effect of a post-thaw dilution, diluting South American silver

99 catfish thawed sperm in 1.1% NaCl (325 mOsm kg⁻¹; pH 7.6; 24 °C) solution on kinetic
100 parameters, morphology, mitochondrial activity, and membrane integrity of sperm cells, as well
101 as on the rates of fertilization, hatching, and normal larvae production.

102 **2. Materials and Methods**

103 *2.1 Fish handling and gametes collection*

104 The experiment was performed at the Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul Research
105 Group AQUAM, Porto Alegre (30°04'24" S; 51°08'11" W), Rio Grande do Sul State, Brazil,
106 during the spawning season (January 2020). Animal handling and experiments were performed
107 according to with the Animal Use Ethics Committee of the Federal University of Rio Grande do
108 Sul (UFRGS), Porto Alegre, RS (N° 39527).

109 Two-year-old South American silver catfish (*R. quelen*) from artificial spawning and
110 breeding were acquired from a commercial fish farm and transported to the laboratory, where they
111 were maintained in concrete tanks (7 m³) in a recirculating system for two months until the
112 experiment. Fish were fed a commercial diet (32% crude protein, Acqua Fish, Supra[®], Alisul,
113 Brazil) twice a day (8:00 and 16:00) until apparent satiety. Animal health and behavior were
114 monitored daily during feeding. Males ($n=8$; 762 ± 168 g of body weight) with detectable running
115 sperm under soft abdominal pressure, and females ($n=4$; 437 ± 131 g) with bulging of the
116 celomathic cavity and reddish urogenital papilla were selected. The breeders were weighed,
117 provided an identification chip, and transferred to two plastic tanks (500 L) in a recirculating
118 system. The experimental parameters were as follows: water temperature, 24 ± 0.5 °C; pH, 7.0 ±
119 0.2; dissolved oxygen, 5.5 ± 0.5 mg L⁻¹; and natural photoperiod (14 h light :10 h dark).

120 The males received a single intraperitoneal dose of carp pituitary extract (CPE) at 3 mg kg
121 ⁻¹, 8 h before sperm collection. Females were induced with two hormonal doses of CPE, with the
122 first dose of 0.5 mg kg⁻¹ at 22 h before collection and the second effective dose at 5 mg kg⁻¹ at 10
123 h (water 24 °C; 240 accumulated thermal units, ATU) before oocyte collection (Sanches et al.,
124 2011a)

125 Before gametes collection, the urogenital papilla and proximities were cleaned and dried
126 to avoid contamination by water, feces, urine, or blood. The sperm was collected in graduated
127 plastic tubes through anteroposterior massage in the abdominal region of the fish. The volume of
128 sperm was recorded, and the samples were kept in a Styrofoam box containing ice foam Super
129 Cold[®] (15 ± 1 °C) (Sanches et al., 2011a) for approximately 30 min. Oocytes were collected in a
130 dry plastic container, and after weighing, one gram of spawned eggs were used for the total
131 estimated oocytes.

132 2.2 Experimental Design

133 The experimental design is summarized in Fig. 1. The experiment was performed using a
134 completely randomized block design with the sperm considered blocks and the male fish as the
135 repetitions. Two treatments were compared: control post-thaw sperm (T1) and post-thaw diluted
136 (T2) sperm. The samples were analyzed through tests of kinetic parameters, sperm morphology,
137 mitochondrial activity, membrane integrity, fertilization, hatching, and normal larvae. All the
138 analyses were performed using one straw for each male ($n=8$) in triplicate. [Figure 1 near here]

139 2.3 Evaluation of fresh sperm

140 Immediately after collection, each sperm sample was subjectively evaluated under a light
141 microscope (Nikon E200, Tokyo, Japan) at $400 \times$ magnification to check for possible previous
142 activation of the spermatozoa by contaminants or water, motility rate (0–100%), and duration of
143 motility (s) (Carolsfeld et al., 2003). A sperm sample from each male (1 μ L) was activated using
144 distilled water (5000 μ L) at a ratio of 1:5000 (sperm: distilled water) (Neumann et al., 2019).

145 The pH of the immobile sperm from each male was evaluated using a pH meter (Quimis
146 Q400HM, Diadema, Brazil). An aliquot (1 mL) of a male sample was pipetted into plastic tubes
147 (1.5 mL) and centrifuged (80-2B Analogic, Daiki, São Paulo, Brazil) at $1000 \times g$ (3341 rpm) for
148 30 min. The osmolality of the seminal plasma (supernatant) was evaluated using an osmometer
149 (Wescor Vapro 5520, Logan, USA). For sperm concentration and morphology, male samples were
150 fixed in 10% buffered formaldehyde solution at a 1:1000 dilution (1 μ L sperm: 999 μ L
151 formaldehyde solution).

152 To evaluate sperm concentration, an aliquot (10 μ L) of diluted sperm was pipetted into each
153 counting field of a Neubauer hemocytometer chamber (Olen, Kasvi, São José dos Pinhais, Brazil)
154 covered by a coverslip for 15 min to stabilize the cells. Using a microscope at $400 \times$ magnification
155 (Nikon E200, Tokyo, Japan) and a manual counter, the gametes were quantified by counting 10
156 squares. After cell counting, the sperm concentration was calculated using the equation described
157 by Sanches et al. (2011b):

158 To evaluate sperm morphology, the samples were diluted in Bengal Rose dye (4%) (Merck,
159 Darmstadt, Germany) at a dilution of 1:10 in a plastic tube (1.5 mL). Smears of 20 μ L of stained
160 sperm were evaluated under an optical microscope at $1000 \times$ magnification (Nikon E200, Tokyo,
161 Japan) (Streit Jr. et al., 2004). Spermatozoa ($n=200$) were evaluated from each sample ($n=8$ males),
162 and the number of normal and abnormal cells was expressed as a percentage. The following
163 morphological changes were evaluated: broken tail, curled tail, strongly curled tail, distally curled
164 tail, short tail, distal and proximal gout, loose head, degenerated head, microcephaly, and

165 macrocephaly (Miliorini et al., 2011).

166 *2.4 Sperm cryopreservation, thawing, and dilution*

167 Only samples with motility greater than 50% were cryopreserved. The sperm of each male
168 was cryopreserved separately within 30 min of collection, following the methodology described
169 by Adames et al. (2015). The freezing medium was composed of 5% D-fructose (Êxodo Científica,
170 Sumaré, Brazil), 5% powdered milk (Molico Skimmed[®], Nestlé, São Paulo, Brazil), and 10%
171 methanol (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). All samples were individually diluted in the freezing
172 medium at a ratio of 1:3 (62.5 µL sperm + 187.5 µL freezing medium). After dilution, the sperm
173 was immediately drawn into 0.25 mL straws (Minitube, Tiefenbach/Landshut, Germany). Straws
174 were conditioned in racks and frozen into a nitrogen vapor vessel (Dry-Shipper MVE SC4/2V,
175 Genex, Toronto, Canada) at -180 °C for 18 h (Carolsfeld et al., 2003). This procedure allows the
176 samples to reach a temperature of -180 °C at 20 minutes, a freezing rate of approximately -160
177 °C min⁻¹. The cooling curve was measured using a digital thermometer (Gulterm 200, Gulton, São
178 Paulo, Brazil) with a sensor PT-100. The samples were subsequently transferred to a cryogenic
179 tank (MVE Millennium 2000, Genex, Toronto, Canada) at -196 °C, and after six months, the
180 straws were thawed in a water bath at 25 °C for 10 s (Adames et al., 2015).

181 Immediately after thawing, each straw was dried, placed in a plastic tube (1.5 mL), and a
182 perforation was made at the top so that the contents flowed into the plastic tube. An aliquot (50
183 µL) was collected and post-thaw diluted in 1000 µL of the NaCl extender (325 mOsm kg⁻¹; pH
184 7.6; 24 °C; diluted in distilled water; Synth, Diadema, Brazil) (T2). The final ratio was 1:20 (sperm
185 + freezing medium: extender). The sperm that remained from the straw was considered the control
186 treatment (T1). Samples were used for analysis or fertilization approximately 2 min after thawing.

187 *2.5 Post-thaw Sperm Analyses*

188 *2.5.1 Kinetics parameters (CASA)*

189 The movement of spermatozoa from the control post-thaw sperm (T1) and the post-thaw
190 diluted sperm (T2) was evaluated using a 1 µL aliquot of each sample. Both were activated by
191 distilled water (24 ± 0.5 °C) in a plastic tube (1.5 mL), with 600 µL for the control and 100 µL for
192 the post-thaw diluted sperm. Immediately after motility was activated, 1 µL was placed in a
193 Neubauer hemocytometer chamber, covered with a coverslip, and placed under a microscope (Bel
194 Solaris, Milan, Italy) at 100 × magnification, connected to a digital video camera (Basler AC640-
195 120uc, 658 × 492 pixels, 120 fps, Ahrensburg, Germany). Analysis of kinetic parameters was
196 performed 10 s after the induction of sperm activation. Pylon Viewer 4 software (Version

197 4.1.0.3660 64-Bit; Basler, Ahrensburg, Germany) was used to video record the spermatozoa
198 movement at a capture rate of 100 fps (Frames Per Second) (Adames et al., 2015). The videos
199 from 10 s after activation were then separated into 50 images using the VirtualDub software
200 (Version 1.10.04; Microsoft Virtual Studio, Redmond, USA), representing 0.5 s of video. The
201 images were analyzed using the Computer-Assisted Sperm Analyzer (CASA) free plugin software
202 from ImageJ (Version 1.53e 64-Bit, National Institutes of Health, USA) (Wilson-Leedy and
203 Ingermann, 2007). The parameters evaluated were motility rate (MOT, %), curvilinear velocity
204 (VCL, $\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$), average path velocity (VAP, $\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$), straight-line velocity (VSL, $\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$),
205 straightness (STR, %), wobble (WOB, %), progression (PROG, $\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$), and beat cross frequency
206 (BCF, Hz). The following input variable values were used in the CASA plugin: a=1; b=40; c=50;
207 d=10; e=3; f=10; g=15; h=5; i=1; j=15; k=15; l=25; m=80; n=80; o=50; p=60; q=50; r=561.7978;
208 s=0; and t=0 (adapted from Neumann et al., 2019).

209 2.5.2 Morphology

210 Control and post-thaw diluted sperm were fixed in 10% buffered formaldehyde solution at
211 a 1:10 dilution (100 μL thawed sperm: 900 μL formaldehyde solution). Spermatozoa morphology
212 was evaluated using the same methodology described for fresh sperm.

213 2.5.3 Mitochondrial Activity

214 Mitochondrial activity was evaluated using MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-
215 diphenyl tetrazolium bromide) (Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA). This
216 technique is based on the reduction of MTT to formazan crystals by the mitochondrial succinyl
217 dehydrogenase enzyme, which is only active in living cells (Liu and Peterson, 1997). The MTT
218 assay was performed according to the adapted method of Mosmann (1983). The samples were
219 thawed, 50 μL of sperm was post-thaw diluted in 1000 μL NaCl extender (325 mOsm kg^{-1} ; pH
220 7.6; 24 °C) into a plastic tube (1.5 mL) (T2), and the remaining sperm in the straw (control) was
221 pipetted into another plastic tube (1.5 mL) without the extender solution (T1). Samples from each
222 male were placed in plastic tubes and centrifuged (80-2B Analogic, Daiki, São Paulo, Brazil) at
223 $1000 \times g$ (3341 rpm) for 10 min. After centrifugation, the supernatant was removed, and 400 μL
224 MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide) (Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher
225 Scientific, Waltham, USA) stock solution (5 mg of MTT mL^{-1} of PBS) was added. After adding
226 MTT, 10 μL of each sample was collected and fixed in 10% buffered formaldehyde solution at a
227 1:100 dilution (10 μL sample: 990 μL formaldehyde solution) to determine the sperm
228 concentration. The samples with MTT were incubated at 28 °C for 2 h, centrifuged, and the
229 supernatant was removed, followed by the addition of 400 μL of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO,

230 Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) and 100 μL of each sample was pipetted into a 96-well microplate
231 (Kasvi, São José dos Pinhais, Brazil). Fifty-one wells were used, 48 for treatments (eight males \times
232 two treatments \times three replicates) and three for the white control, which was subjected to the same
233 treatments except that the sperm was not pipetted.

234 The optical density of the samples was measured using a spectrophotometer (SpectraMax
235 M2[®], San Jose, USA) at a wavelength of 570 nm. The MTT reduction rate (optical density) for
236 each sample was calculated by determining the difference between the sample and control values.
237 The results were normalized to 50 million cells, as adapted from (Aziz, 2006).

238 *2.5.4 Membrane Integrity*

239 The samples ($n=8$) were thawed, and 50 μL of the control sperm (T1) was centrifuged
240 (K14-1215, Kasvi, São José dos Pinhas, Brazil) at $1000 \times g$ 10 min^{-1} . After centrifugation, 25 μL
241 was diluted in 75 μL of NaCl solution (325 mOsm kg^{-1} ; pH 7.6; $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, diluted in distilled water),
242 and 50 μL was stained. For post-thaw diluted treatment (T2), 10 μL of sperm after thawed was
243 immediately diluted in 190 μL of NaCl solution and centrifuged (K14-1215, Kasvi, São José dos
244 Pinhas, Brazil) at $1000 \times g$ 10 min^{-1} . After the supernatant was discarded, the sample was
245 resuspended in 200 μL of saline solution. Finally, 25 μL of the solution was diluted in 25 μL of
246 saline solution and stained.

247 The membrane integrity was assessed by a staining procedure using SYBR-14 (Thermo
248 Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA), which penetrates through the membrane of live cells and stains
249 them green, and propidium iodide (PI; Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA), which
250 penetrates through the ruptured membrane of dead cells and stains them red. For staining, 50 μL
251 of each sample was mixed with 0.25 μL SYBR-14 (0.02 mM) and incubated in the dark at room
252 temperature ($\sim 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) for 4 min. Then, 1 μL PI (1.19 mM) was added and incubated for 1 min in
253 the dark at room temperature ($\sim 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). This methodology was adapted from Hagedorn et al.
254 (2009). Before analyzing the samples, was added 1950 μL of NaCl solution.

255 The evaluation was performed using an Accuri C6 flow cytometer (BD Biosciences, San
256 Jose, USA) equipped with a 488 nm solid state laser and a 640 nm diode laser. Fluorescence signals
257 of SYBR-14 were gathered via a 533/30 nm band-pass filter, and PI was collected using a 670 nm
258 long-pass filter. Prior to the analyses, the flow cytometer was adjusted using a sperm sample that
259 was heated to 100°C per 40s and then exposed to liquid nitrogen at -196°C causing death (100%)
260 of cells (positive control). This sperm sample was stained only with PI, and the mortality of all
261 cells was verified under a fluorescence microscope. The entire sperm population of South
262 American silver catfish could be identified and gated. The results were plotted on a logarithmic

263 scale (C6 Analysis Software, BD Biosciences, San Jose, USA). The sperm population was gated
264 by referring to the expected forward- and side-scatter signals. Ten thousand events per sample
265 were acquired.

266 *2.5.5 Fertilization, hatching and normal larvae*

267 The oocytes were collected from each female ($n=4$), and through visual evaluation, one
268 spawning was chosen to be fertilized by the control sperm (T1), post-thaw diluted sperm (T2), and
269 fresh sperm. A fresh sperm pool from three males was formed and used for quality control of
270 oocytes. The motility and concentration of the control sperm (T1), post-thaw diluted sperm (T2),
271 and sperm pool were analyzed following the same methodology as previously described. Firstly
272 0.2 mL of oocytes (223.1 ± 4.1 oocytes) was placed into 51 disposable plastic cups (50 mL) (eight
273 males \times two treatments \times three replicates and three controls with fresh sperm). A volume of control
274 sperm (T1), post-thaw diluted (T2), or fresh sperm was then pipetted into each cup to reach an
275 ideal motile sperm: oocyte ratio of 70000 motile spermatozoa per oocyte (Neumann et al., 2019).
276 The activation was promoted individually with 20 mL of distilled water ($24 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). A
277 subsequent mixing action was imposed on the gametes for 60 s, followed by the transfer of oocytes
278 and spermatozoa to small circular sieves.

279 The eggs were incubated in small circular sieves with nylon nets in plastic tanks (500 L) in
280 a recirculating system. The experimental parameters were as follows: water temperature, 24 ± 0.5
281 $^\circ\text{C}$; pH, 7.5 ± 0.2 ; dissolved oxygen $5.5 \pm 0.5 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$.

282 The fertilization rates were evaluated after the embryonic blastopore closed, at
283 approximately 12 h after fertilization (Pereira et al., 2006). Analysis was performed by counting
284 the number of fertilized and non-fertilized oocytes, so all oocytes from each sieve were analyzed
285 using a binocular stereomicroscope (Q7740SZ-T, Quimis, Diadema, Brazil) at $10 \times$ and a manual
286 counter. The result is given by the formula $\text{Fertilization (\%)} = (\text{Number of fertilized}/\text{Total oocytes})$
287 $\times 100$.

288 Hatching rates and normal larvae were observed 48 h after fertilization. The analyses were
289 performed by counting all the larvae and classifying their morphology. Larvae without head, spine,
290 and yolk sac abnormalities were considered normal (Jeziarska et al., 2009). A binocular
291 stereomicroscope was used at $10 \times$ and a manual counter. The results are given by the formulas
292 $\text{Hatching (\%)} = (\text{Number of larvae}/\text{Total oocytes}) \times 100$ and $\text{Normal Larvae (\%)} = (\text{Number of}$
293 $\text{normal larvae}/\text{Total larvae}) \times 100$.

294 *2.6 Statistical analyses*

295 Data are expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Data were tested for normal

296 distribution using the Shapiro–Wilk test and homogeneity using the Bartlett test. After verifying
 297 compliance with the statistical assumptions, data were analyzed using a one-way ANOVA,
 298 followed by comparing the paired t-test averages. The level of significance for all statistical tests
 299 was set at 95% ($P < 0.05$). Statistical analysis and graph construction were performed using
 300 GraphPad Prism 7.04 (GraphPad Software Inc., 2017).

301 **3. Results**

302 *3.1 Evaluation of fresh sperm*

303 The sperm characteristics were: volume 13 ± 4 mL, concentration $5.9 \pm 2.1 \times 10^{10}$
 304 spermatozoa mL^{-1} , pH 8.1 ± 0.06 , and osmolality 286 ± 7 mOsm kg^{-1} . Fresh sperm presented a
 305 subjective motility of $80 \pm 27\%$ and a motility duration of 46 ± 17 seconds. The analysis of sperm
 306 morphology showed $86.5 \pm 5.7\%$ of spermatozoa as normal or with abnormalities (Fig. 3).

307 *3.2 Post-thaw Sperm Analyses*

308 *3.2.1 Kinetics parameters (CASA)*

309 The motility of the control sperm samples ($51 \pm 12\%$) did not differ ($P > 0.05$) from the post-
 310 thaw diluted samples ($57 \pm 14\%$) in NaCl solution (Fig. 2A). Higher velocities were observed
 311 when samples were post-thaw diluted in NaCl (VCL, 69 ± 11 $\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$; VAP, 45 ± 8 $\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$; VSL,
 312 43 ± 8 $\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$) compared to the control samples (VCL, 47 ± 10 $\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$; VAP, 31 ± 6 $\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$; VSL,
 313 30 ± 6 $\mu\text{m s}^{-1}$) (Fig. 2B). Higher straightness (STR), progression (PROG), and beat cross frequency
 314 (BCF) were observed in the post-thaw diluted samples (STR, $96 \pm 7\%$; PROG, 666 ± 128 μm ;
 315 BCF, 42 ± 2 Hz) than in their control sperm counterparts (STR, $95 \pm 5\%$; PROG, 463 ± 92 $\mu\text{m s}$,
 316 BCF, 40 ± 2 Hz) (Fig. 2C, 2D, and 2E). There was no difference in wobble (WOB) between control
 317 ($67 \pm 5\%$) and post-thaw diluted ($65 \pm 7\%$) sperm (Fig. 2C). [Figure 2A, 2B, 2C, 2D and 2E near
 318 here]

319 *3.2.2 Morphology*

320 The number of normal spermatozoa in the control samples ($17 \pm 8\%$) and post-thaw diluted
 321 samples ($24 \pm 8\%$) did not differ ($P > 0.05$). The strongly curled tail was the only change that
 322 differed significantly between the control ($2 \pm 1\%$) and post-thaw diluted ($5 \pm 2\%$) samples (Fig.
 323 3). [Figure 3 near here]

324 *3.2.3 Mitochondrial Activity*

325 The mitochondrial activity showed that the control (0.17 ± 0.05 Abs s^{-1}) and post-thaw
 326 diluted (0.2 ± 0.04 Abs s^{-1}) samples did not differ (Fig 4A). [Figure 4 near here]

327 3.2.4 Membrane Integrity

328 There was no difference in the membrane integrity of control ($59 \pm 10\%$) and post-thaw
329 diluted ($64 \pm 11\%$) sperm (Fig. 4B).

330 3.2.5 Fertilization, hatching and normal larvae

331 The fertilization rate with a pool of fresh sperm (91%) showed that the spawning used was
332 of good quality. A higher fertilization rate was observed when used post-thaw diluted sperm in
333 NaCl solution ($93 \pm 3\%$) compared to control ($65 \pm 13\%$) (Fig 4C). The same occurred for hatching
334 rate, whereby control sperm ($55 \pm 17\%$) had a lower rate than post-thaw diluted samples ($82 \pm 9\%$)
335 (Fig 4C). For the normal larvae production rate, the control ($89 \pm 10\%$) and post-thaw diluted (89
336 $\pm 7\%$) samples did not differ (Fig 4C). **Oocytes from only one female were used, limiting these**
337 **results' interpretation.** [Figure 4 near here]

338 4. Discussion

339 Sperm cryopreservation is biotechnology that subjects cells to contact with toxic solutions
340 and extremely low temperatures. These actions cause damage and decrease sperm quality after
341 thawing, compromising fertilization and hatching rates. Thus, methodologies that mitigate these
342 damages are always welcome. Post-thaw dilution in NaCl for thawed sperm is practical and
343 inexpensive. Consequently, comparing sperm quality and reproductive capacity between control
344 and post-thaw diluted sperm from the same straw is relevant. Using post-thaw dilution in a NaCl
345 solution improved the kinetic parameters, maintained the membrane integrity and mitochondrial
346 activity of sperm, and provided a higher fertilization and hatching rate.

347 The choice of NaCl solution's ionic composition, osmolality, and temperature was based on
348 sperm characteristics to maintain sperm quality. Thus, NaCl-based was used since most of the ions
349 in South American silver catfish seminal plasma are Na^+ and Cl^- (Borges et al., 2005). The
350 osmolality of the seminal plasma of fresh sperm was $287 \pm 7 \text{ mOsm kg}^{-1}$; hence, to avoid sperm
351 activation before fertilization, the NaCl solution osmolality was corrected to 325 mOsm kg^{-1} , and
352 the temperature was maintained at 24°C , which was the same temperature in which the animals
353 were immersed until the moment of gamete collection. Thus, when thawed sperm samples were
354 post-thaw diluted in NaCl, the ionic properties and temperature did not show substantial changes
355 that could damage the gametes.

356 Methanol is a permeable cryoprotectant that enters cells through the pores of the cell
357 membrane. Higher concentrations, medium temperatures, and exposure times can acidify the
358 intracellular medium, which is toxic to cells (Best, 2015). Therefore, post-thaw dilution in NaCl

359 solution decreased the methanol concentration in the medium, consequently decreasing its toxicity
360 to gametes at room temperature (~25 °C) (Morris et al., 2012).

361 The analysis of sperm kinetic parameters is widely used to compare different experimental
362 conditions (Gallego and Asturiano, 2018). For example, in a study with cats, sperm motility was
363 greater in diluted samples (65.4%) than in undiluted samples (59.2%). In addition, diluted sperm
364 also had a higher progressive motility score (4.1) than undiluted sperm (3.6) (Chatdarong et al.,
365 2010). Although our data showed no difference between treatments for motility rate, post-thaw
366 dilution in NaCl provided better parameters for sperm velocity. The higher sperm velocities may
367 be different at the time of oocyte fertilization. In other studies, on *Rhamdia quelen* (Neumann et
368 al., 2019), *Prochilodus lineatus* (Viveiros et al., 2010), and *Solea senegalensis* (Beirão et al.,
369 2015), a high correlation between sperm velocities and fertilization rate has been reported. The
370 progression observed in the post-thaw sperm diluted may have another factor that influenced the
371 higher fertilization rate. The spermatozoa must move close to the oocyte for fertilization (Cosson
372 et al., 2008). Therefore, the progression parameter, which indicates the total average distance
373 traveled by spermatozoa, is a key factor for fertilization.

374 There is a classic definition by Morisawa et al. (1983) that sperm activation of carp in
375 hypoosmotic saline solution strongly reduces sperm tail curling, which even led to the formulation
376 of a diluent solution for the species by Saad and Billard (1987). Thus, we expected that the South
377 American silver catfish post-thawed sperm would present a higher percentage of flagellum (tail)
378 abnormalities and not when previously post-thaw diluted in a hypoosmotic solution of NaCl in
379 relation to the cryopreservation solution in which it was submitted. This behavior did not occur
380 with this species, but a significant percentage, albeit low, of the strongly curled tail abnormality.
381 In the review of flagellum function in fish sperm by Boryshpolets et al. (2018), the authors related
382 the study by Perchec et al. (1995) that determined osmotic damage as the main factor that causes
383 alteration in sperm flagella. However, in fishes, sperm motility is usually activated by osmotic
384 shock (Alavi and Cosson, 2006).

385 In general, the highest percentage of abnormality is always associated with lower motility of
386 post-thawed sperm, as their structure and physiological function have been damaged, resulting in
387 a loss of potential function for kinetics parameters (Muchlisin and Azizah, 2009). So, in our study,
388 a direct consequence of the increase in the strongly curled tail abnormality could be related to
389 some sperm kinetics parameters or even to the productive parameters (fertilization, hatching, and
390 normal larvae rates). However, in none of these other evaluated parameters, there was a lower
391 mean percentage in post-thawed sperm post-thaw diluted in NaCl compared to control. In South
392 American silver catfish, it has already been proven that the appearance of a strongly curled tail is

393 associated with the physic-chemical actions to which sperm are exposed, mainly the
394 cryopreservation process (Da Costa et al., 2019).

395 Membrane integrity is essential for sperm functions and is used as a sperm quality parameter
396 (Cabrita et al., 2014). The sperm membrane of fish sperm is sensitive to small changes in the
397 osmolality of the environment (Boryshpolets et al., 2020). It was expected that the post-thaw
398 dilution could cause damage to the sperm membrane. However, comparing the integrity of the
399 sperm membrane of the two treatments, we did not observe a difference. The same was presented
400 when silver catfish post-thaw sperm was diluted in Ginsburg and centrifuged (Pérez-Atehortúa et
401 al., 2022). Hence, the sperm membrane of the silver catfish is resistant to osmotic shock, as proven
402 by post-thaw dilution.

403 In sperm, as in other cells, mitochondria are the organelle responsible for providing energy
404 in the form of ATP (Boryshpolets et al., 2020). The success of fertilization and the duration of
405 sperm motility are dependent on mitochondrial activity (Figuroa et al., 2019). Our results did not
406 show a difference in mitochondrial activity between treatments. On the other hand, another study
407 by our group (Pérez-Atehortúa et al., 2022) showed greater mitochondrial activity of post-thaw
408 sperm diluted compared to undiluted. The difference between the results found in the studies may
409 be due to the use of an extender containing other salts besides NaCl and a sperm pool. However,
410 we know that mitochondrial activity was not the key to explaining the high fertilization using post-
411 thaw diluted sperm in the present study.

412 The presence of permeable cryoprotectant at fertilization is toxic to oocytes and sperm,
413 which can compromise sperm/oocyte interaction or embryonic development. At the same time, it
414 can cause non-lethal damage to spermatozoa, which does not affect motility but reduces their
415 ability to fertilize (Boryshpolets et al., 2020). Post-thaw dilution provided greater sperm velocity
416 and decreased permeable cryoprotectant concentration at the time of fertilization, resulting in a
417 high fertilization rate (>80%) (Beirão et al., 2019). In another study carried out by our group
418 (Pérez-Atehortúa et al., 2022), **fertilizing oocytes from one female. The** post-thawed sperm of
419 silver catfish diluted in the Ginsburg extender and centrifuged showed fertilization (76.68%) and
420 hatching rates (54.62%) lower than the present study. This showed us that centrifugation of post-
421 thaw diluted sperm is unnecessary to achieve high fertilization and hatching rates. **The fact that**
422 **we used oocytes from only one female in fertilization limits the interpretation of our results, but**
423 **the use of dilution in the present study showed the highest rates of fertilization (93%) and hatching**
424 **(82%) ever reported for this species.** We did not find differences in the normal larvae rate using
425 the thawed sperm samples from the control and post-thaw diluted treatments. Other studies that
426 used thawed sperm of the same species also observed an offspring of more than 90% of normal

427 larvae (Neumann et al., 2019; Pérez-Atehortúa et al., 2022). Therefore, we believe that the
 428 emergence of South American silver catfish larvae with morphological problems is not related to
 429 the use of cryopreserved sperm.

430 5. Conclusion

431 The post-thaw dilution of South American silver catfish sperm in NaCl solution (325 mOsm
 432 kg⁻¹; pH 7.6; 24 °C) improved the sperm kinetic parameters, as well as fertilization and hatching
 433 rates. **Our reproductive results are limited because we use oocytes from only one female even
 434 though** this methodology can be included in the sperm cryopreservation protocols for this species
 435 and should be investigated for other species concerning their seminal properties, hence improving
 436 cryopreservation protocols for fish sperm.

437 Acknowledgments

438 We would like to thank the Brazilian fostering agencies FAPERGS (N° 17/2551-0000917-7),
 439 CAPES/PROEX (N° 88882.346090/2015-1), CNPq (N° 141717/2019-0). The authors warmly
 440 thank the UNESP Fish Reproduction Research, UFRGS Reproduction Bioethics Laboratory,
 441 UNIVATES Laboratory of Animal Reproduction Biotechnology and the people who are part of
 442 the AQUAM Laboratory in UFRGS and Fish Reproduction Research in UNESP who helped in all
 443 collection and analysis of sperm samples.

444 Author Contribution Statement

445 **Thales de Souza França:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Investigation,
 446 Writing - Original Draft, Visualization, Project administration **Itamar Cossina Gomes:**
 447 Conceptualization; Investigation **Eduardo Antônio Sanches:** Methodology; Formal analysis;
 448 Investigation; Resources, Validation **Maritza Pérez Atehortúa:** Investigation **Nathalia Santos**
 449 **Teixeira:** Investigation **Rômulo Batista Rodrigues:** Conceptualization, Methodology,
 450 Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing. **Thaiza Rodrigues de Freitas:** Investigation **Andrea**
 451 **Giannotti Galuppo:** Methodology, Investigation **Monike Quirino:** Investigation **Jhony Lisbôa**
 452 **Benato:** Investigation **Thales Lysakowski Flores Machado:** Investigation **Lis Santos Marques:**
 453 Writing - Review & Editing **Ivan Cunha Bustamante-Filho** Resources **Fernando Pandolfo**
 454 **Bortolozzo:** Resources **Danilo Pedro Streit Jr:** Conceptualization, Resources, Writing - Review
 455 & Editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition

456 Conflicts of interest

457 We declare no actual or potential conflict of interest regarding the submitting manuscript.

458 References

459

460 Adames, M.S., de Toledo, C.P.R., Neumann, G., Buzzi, A.H., Buratto, C.N., Piana, P.A., Bombardelli,
 461 R.A., 2015. Optimization of the sperm: Oocyte ratio and sperm economy in the artificial reproduction
 462 of *Rhamdia quelen* using fructose as a sperm motility modulator. Anim. Reprod. Sci. 161, 119–128.
 463 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anireprosci.2015.08.014>

- 464 Alavi, S.M.H., Cosson, J., 2006. Sperm motility in fishes. (II) Effects of ions and osmolality: A review.
465 Cell Bio. Intern. 30, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cellbi.2005.06.004>
- 466 Alvarenga, M.A., Papa, F.O., Carmo, M.T., Kievitsbosch, T., Castro Chaves, M.M.B., Ramires Neto, C.,
467 2012. Methods of Concentrating Stallion Semen. J. of Equi. Vet. Sci. 32, 424–429.
468 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jevs.2012.06.003>
- 469 Alvarez, J.G., Lasso, J.L., Blasco, L., Nuñez, R.C., Heyner, S., Caballero, P.P., Storey, B.T., 1993.
470 Centrifugation of human spermatozoa induces sublethal damage; separation of human spermatozoa
471 from seminal plasma by a dextran swim-up procedure without centrifugation extends their motile
472 lifetime. Hum. Reprod. 8, 1087–1092. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordjournals.humrep.a138198>
- 473 Aziz, D.M., 2006. Assessment of bovine sperm viability by MTT reduction assay. Anim. Reprod. Sci. 92,
474 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anireprosci.2005.05.029>
- 475 Beirão, J., Soares, F., Pousão-Ferreira, P., Diogo, P., Dias, J., Dinis, M.T., Herráez, M.P., Cabrita, E., 2015.
476 The effect of enriched diets on *Solea senegalensis* sperm quality. Aquaculture 435, 187–194.
477 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2014.09.025>
- 478 Beirão, J., Boulais, M., Gallego, V., O'Brien, J.K., Peixoto, S., Robeck, T.R., Cabrita, E., 2019. Sperm
479 handling in aquatic animals for artificial reproduction. Theriogenology 133, 161–178.
480 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.theriogenology.2019.05.004>
- 481 Best, B.P., 2015. Cryoprotectant Toxicity: Facts, Issues, and Questions. Rejuv. Res. 18, 422–436.
482 <https://doi.org/10.1089/rej.2014.1656>
- 483 Borges, A., Rodrigues Siqueira, D., Follmann Jurinitz, D., Zanini, R., do Amaral, F., Lacerda Grillo, M.,
484 Oberst, E.R., Wassermann, G.F., 2005. Biochemical composition of seminal plasma and annual
485 variations in semen characteristics of jundiá *Rhamdia quelen* (Quoy and Gaimard, Pimelodidae). Fish
486 Phys. and Bioch. 31, 45–53. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10695-005-4742-8>
- 487 Boryshpolets, S., Kholodnyy, V., Cosson, J., Dzyuba, B., 2018. Fish sperm motility analysis: The central
488 role of the flagellum. Reprod., Fert. and Devel. 30, 833–841. <https://doi.org/10.1071/RD17478>
- 489 Boryshpolets, S., Kholodnyy, V., Cosson, J., Dzyuba, B., 2020. Fish sperm quality evaluation after
490 cryopreservation, in Betsy, J., Kumar, S. (Eds.), Cryopreservation of Fish Gametes. Springer Nature
491 Singapore Pte Ltd., The Gateway, pp. 117-133. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-4025-7_5
- 492 Cabrita, E., Martínez-Páramo, S., Gavaia, P.J., Riesco, M.F., Valcarce, D.G., Sarasquete, C., Herráez, M.P.,
493 Robles, V., 2014. Factors enhancing fish sperm quality and emerging tools for sperm analysis.
494 Aquaculture 432, 389–401. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2014.04.034>
- 495 Carolsfeld, J., Godinho, H.P., Zaniboni Filho, E., Harvey, B.J., 2003. Cryopreservation of sperm in
496 Brazilian migratory fish conservation. J. of Fish Biol. 63, 472–489. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1095-8649.2003.00170.x>
- 498 Chatdarong, K., Thuwanut, P., Manee-in, S., Lohachit, C., Axné, E., 2010. Effects of thawing temperature
499 and post-thaw dilution on the quality of cat spermatozoa. Reprod. in Dom. Anim 45, 221–227.
500 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0531.2008.01218.x>
- 501 Cosson, J., Groison, A.L., Suquet, M., Fauvel, C., Dreanno, C., Billard, R., 2008. Marine fish spermatozoa:
502 Racing ephemeral swimmers. Reproduction 136, 277–294. <https://doi.org/10.1530/REP-07-0522>
- 503 Da Costa, B.B., Marques, L.S., Lassen, P.G., Rodrigues, R.B., Streit, D.P., 2019. Cryopreservation-induced
504 morphological changes in the sperm of South American silver catfish (*Rhamdia quelen*). J. of Appl.
505 Ichth. 35, 987–993. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jai.13928>

- 506 Di Chiacchio, I.M., Almeida, I.L.G., Leal, M.C., Viveiros, A.T.M., 2017. Sperm quality and its freezing
507 ability throughout the spawning season in *Prochilodus lineatus* and *Brycon orbignyanus*.
508 *Theriogenology* 90, 284–288. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.theriogenology.2016.12.011>
- 509 Egger, R.C., Motta, N.C., França, T. de S., de Oliveira, A.V., Fernandes-Braga, W., Alvarez-Leite, J.I.,
510 Murgas, L.D.S., 2021. Sperm cryopreservation of *Prochilodus lineatus* throughout the same
511 reproductive season. *Aqua. Rese.* 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1111/are.15513>
- 512 Figueroa, E., Merino, O., Risopatrón, J., Isachenko, V., Sánchez, R., Effer, B., Isachenko, E., Farias, J.G.,
513 Valdebenito, I., 2015. Effect of seminal plasma on Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) sperm vitrification.
514 *Theriogenology* 83, 238-245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.theriogenology.2014.09.015>
- 515 Figueroa, E., Lee-Estevez, M., Valdebenito, I., Watanabe, I., Oliveira, R.P.S., Romero, J., Castillo, R.L.,
516 Farias, J.G., 2019. Effects of cryopreservation on mitochondrial function and sperm quality in fish.
517 *Aquaculture* 511, 634190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2019.06.004>
- 518 França, T.S., Motta, N.C., Egger, R.C., Oliveira, A. v., Murgas, L.D.S., 2020. Impact of activation solutions
519 on fresh and frozen-thawed sperm motility and fertilization success for two species of migratory
520 freshwater fishes. *Theriogenology* 149, 6–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.theriogenology.2020.03.016>
- 521 Gallego, V., Asturiano, J.F., 2018. Sperm motility in fish: Technical applications and perspectives through
522 CASA-Mot systems. *Reprod., Fert. and Devel.* 30, 820–832. <https://doi.org/10.1071/RD17460>
- 523 Gil Barcellos, L.J., Kreutz, L.C., Quevedo, R.M., Fioreze, I., Cericato, L., Soso, A.B., Fagundes, M.,
524 Conrad, J., Baldissera, R.K., Bruschi, A., Ritter, F., 2004. Nursery rearing of jundiá, *Rhamdia quelen*
525 (Quoy & Gaimard) in cages: Cage type, stocking density and stress response to confinement.
526 *Aquaculture* 232, 383–394. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0044-8486\(03\)00545-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0044-8486(03)00545-3)
- 527 Hagedorn, M., Ricker, J., McCarthy, M., Meyers, S.A., Tiersch, T.R., Varga, Z.M., Kleinhans, F.W., 2009.
528 Biophysics of zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) sperm. *Cryobiology* 58, 12–19.
529 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cryobiol.2008.09.013>
- 530 Jezierska, B., Ługowska, K., Witeska, M., 2009. The effects of heavy metals on embryonic development
531 of fish (a review). *Fish Phys. and Bioch.* 35, 625–640. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10695-008-9284-4>
- 532 Liu, Y., Peterson, D., 1997. Mechanism of cellular 3-(4, 5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2, 5-diphenyltetrazolium
533 bromide (MTT) reduction. *J. of Neuroch.* 69, 581–93. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1471-4159.1997.69020581.x>
- 535 López, D.I., Leal, M.C., Viveiros, A.T.M., 2015. Extender composition and osmolality affects post-thaw
536 motility and velocities of piracanjuba *Brycon orbignyanus* (Valenciennes, 1850) (Characiformes)
537 sperm. *J. of Appl. Ichth.* 31, 114–118. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jai.12743>
- 538 Martínez-Páramo, S., Horváth, Á., Labbé, C., Zhang, T., Robles, V., Herráez, P., Suquet, M., Adams, S.,
539 Viveiros, A., Tiersch, T.R., Cabrita, E., 2017. Cryobanking of aquatic species HHS Public Access.
540 *Aquaculture* 472, 156–177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2016.05.042>. Cryobanking
- 541 Miliorini, A.B., Murgas, L.D.S., Rosa, P.V., Oberlender, G., Pereira, G.J.M., Da Costa, D.V., 2011. A
542 morphological classification proposal for curimba (*Prochilodus lineatus*) sperm damages after
543 cryopreservation. *Aqua. Rese.* 42, 177–187. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2109.2010.02575.x>
- 544 Morisawa, M., Suzuki, K., Shimizu, H., Morisawa, S., Yasuda, K., 1983. Effects of osmolality and
545 potassium on motility of spermatozoa from freshwater cyprinid fishes. *J. of Exp. Biol.*, 95–103.
546 <https://doi.org/10.1242/jeb.107.1.95>
- 547 Morris, J.G., Acton, E., Murray, B.J., Fonseca, F., 2012. Freezing injury: The special case of the sperm cell.
548 *Cryobiology* 64, 71–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cryobiol.2011.12.002>

- 549 Mosmann, T., 1983. Rapid Colorimetric Assay for Cellular Growth and Survival: Application to
550 Proliferation and Cytotoxicity Assays. *J. of Immun. Meth.* 65, 55–63.
551 <https://doi.org/10.1039/c6ra17788c>
- 552 Muchlisin, Z.A., Azizah, M.N.S., 2009. Influence of cryoprotectants on abnormality and motility of baung
553 (*Mystus nemurus*) spermatozoa after long-term cryopreservation. *Cryobiology* 58, 166–169.
554 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cryobiol.2008.11.010>
- 555 Neumann, G., Sanches, P.V., Bombardelli, R.A., 2019. Effects on fertility of motile sperm to egg ratio with
556 use of cryopreserved *Rhamdia quelen* semen at different post-activation times. *Anim. Reprod. Sci.*
557 201, 84–92. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anireprosci.2019.01.001>
- 558 Orfão, L.H., Nascimento, A.F., Corrêa, F.M., Cosson, J., Viveiros, A.T.M., 2011. Extender composition,
559 osmolality and cryoprotectant effects on the motility of sperm in the Brazilian endangered species
560 *Brycon opalinus* (Characiformes). *Aquaculture* 311, 241–247.
561 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2010.11.041>
- 562 Peixe-BR, 2020. Anuário da Piscicultura 2020. Associação Brasileira de Piscicultura 1, 1–136.
- 563 Perchec, G., Jeulin, C., Cosson, J., Andre, F., Billard, R., 1995. Relationship between sperm ATP content
564 and motility of carp spermatozoa. *J. of Cell Sci.* 108, 747–753.
- 565 Pereira, C.R., Barcellos, L.J.G., Kreutz, L.C., Quevedo, R.M., Ritter, F., Silva, L.B., 2006. Embryonic and
566 larval development of jundiá (*Rhamdia quelen*, Quoy & Gaimard, 1824, Pisces, Teleostei), a South
567 American catfish. *Braz. J. of Biol.* 66, 1057–1063. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1519-69842006000600013>
- 569 Pérez-Atehortúa, M., Galuppo, A.G., Rodrigues, R.B., França, T.S., Teixeira, N. S., Freitas, T.R., Marques,
570 L.S., Gomes, I.C., Benato, J.L., Flores, T., Sanches, E.A., Souza, A.R.S., Bustamante, I., Quirino, M.,
571 Bortolozzo, F. P, Streit Jr., D.P., 2022. The use of differential separation and density gradient with
572 AllGrad 90% after thawing improves the sperm quality of South American catfish (*Rhamdia quelen*).
573 *Aquaculture* 553. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2022.738072>
- 574 Saad, A., Billard, R., 1987. Composition et emploi d'un dilueur d'insémination chez la carpe, *Cyprinus*
575 *carpio*. *Aquaculture* 66, 329–345. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0044-8486\(87\)90117-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0044-8486(87)90117-7)
- 576 Sanches, E.A., Neumann, G., De Toledo, C.P.R., Bombardelli, R.A., Piana, P.A., Romagosa, E., 2011a.
577 Temperature and storage period over spermatoc parameters of jundiá, *Rhamdia quelen* (Quoy &
578 Gaimard, 1824). *Aqua. Rese.* 44, 534–541. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2109.2011.03056.x>
- 579 Sanches, E.A., Marcos, R.M., Baggio, D.M., Tessaro, L., Balen, R.E., Bombardelli, R.A., 2011b.
580 Estimativa da concentração espermática do sêmen de peixe pelo método de espermatócrito. *Revista*
581 *Brasileira de Zootecnia* 40, 1163–1167. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1516-35982011000600001>
- 582 Streit Jr., D., Moraes, G., Ribeiro, R., Povh, J., Souza, E., 2004. Avaliação de diferentes técnicas para
583 coloração de sêmen de peixes. *Arq. ciênc. vet. zool. UNIPAR* 157–162.
584 <https://doi.org/10.25110/arqvet.v7i2.2004.82>
- 585 Tabares, C., Tarazona, A., Olivera Ángel, M., 2005. Fisiología de la activación del espermatozoide en peces
586 de agua dulce. *Rev. Colom. de Cien. Pec.* 18, 149–161.
- 587 Valladão, G.M.R., Gallani, S.U., Pilarski, F., 2018. South American fish for continental aquaculture. *Rev.*
588 *in Aquac.* 10, 351–369. <https://doi.org/10.1111/raq.12164>
- 589 Viveiros, A.T.M., Godinho, H.P., 2009. Sperm quality and cryopreservation of Brazilian freshwater fish
590 species: A review. *Fish Phys. and Bioch.* 35, 137–150. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10695-008-9240-3>

591 Viveiros, A.T.M., Nascimento, A.F., Orfão, L.H., Isaú, Z.A., 2010. Motility and fertility of the subtropical
 592 freshwater fish streaked prochilod (*Prochilodus lineatus*) sperm cryopreserved in powdered coconut
 593 water. *Theriogenology* 74, 551–556. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.theriogenology.2010.03.018>

594 Viveiros, A.T.M., Motta, N.C., Isaú, Z.A., Almeida, I.L.G., Leal, M.C., 2019. Ions and osmolality on post-
 595 thaw sperm motility activation of the endangered *Brycon insignis* (Characiformes). *J. of Appl. Ichth.*
 596 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jai.13857>

597 Wilson-Leedy, J.G., Ingermann, R.L., 2007. Development of a novel CASA system based on open source
 598 software for characterization of zebrafish sperm motility parameters. *Theriogenology* 67, 661–672.
 599 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.theriogenology.2006.10.003>

600

601

602

603

604

605

606

607

608

609

610

611

612

613

614

615

616 [Colour should be used]

617 Figure 1 – Experimental design to compare quality and reproductive capacity of control post-thaw
 618 *R. quelen* sperm (T1) and post-thaw diluted sperm in NaCl solution (T2). After the collect sperm
 619 samples from each male ($n = 8$) and before its cryopreservation, the quality of the samples was
 620 validated by means of sperm motility percentage, sperm motility duration, sperm concentration
 621 and sperm morphology (normal spermatozoa anomalies percentage). The straws from each male
 622 were individually thawed, immediately one part of sperm into the straw was used (T1) and un
 623 aliquot (50 μ L) of the same sample was post-thaw diluted in 1 mL of NaCl solution (325 mOsm
 624 kg^{-1} ; pH 7.6; 24°C, diluted in distilled water) (T2). The same parameters were evaluated for each
 625 treatment, kinetics parameters, morphology, mitochondrial activity, membrane integrity
 626 fertilization, fertilization rate, hatching rate and normal larvae rate. For all analysis was performed
 627 using one straw per male in triplicate.

628

629 Figure 2. Motility rate (A), velocities (curvilinear, VCL; average path, VAP; straight-line, VSL)
 630 (B), straightness (STR) and wobble (WOB) (C), progression (D), and beat cross frequency (E) of
 631 the control thawed sperm (T1) ($n=8$) and that post-thaw diluted in NaCl solution (T2) ($n=8$)
 632 assessed by CASA. Bars indicate mean \pm SD; Means followed by different numbers of asterisks
 633 differ ** $p<0.01$; *** $p<0.001$, **** $p<0.0001$; paired t-test).

634

635 Figure 3. Morphology of fresh sperm ($n=8$), control thawed sperm ($n=8$), and post-thaw diluted in
 636 NaCl solution ($n=8$) analyzed by Rose Bengal (4%) stain, observed and counted using an optical
 637 microscope ($1000\times$ magnification) and manual counter, respectively. Bars indicate mean \pm SD; *
 638 Means followed by an asterisk differ between control and post-thaw diluted ($p < 0.05$; paired t-
 639 test).

640

641 Figure 4. Mitochondrial activity (A) analyzed by MTT reduction rate (optical density) at 570 nm.
 642 The results were normalized to 50 million cells. Membrane integrity (B) analyzed by flow
 643 cytometry. The cells with intact membrane were stained green using SYBR-14 and the cells with
 644 rupture membrane were stained red using propidium iodide (PI). Fertilization, hatching, and
 645 normal larvae rate (C) were obtained after counting and evaluating all oocytes and larvae collected
 646 in sieves. All assessments were evaluated the sperm ($n=8$) from control post-thaw sperm and post-
 647 thaw diluted in NaCl solution. Bars indicate mean \pm SD; Means followed by different numbers of
 648 asterisks differ ** $p<0.01$; **** $p<0.0001$; paired t-test).

649